

Title: (Re-) Architecting for Enabling and Supporting DevOps

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General Information

This case study aims to “*investigate the practices and tools that enable architecting for successful adoption of DevOps*”.

Interview guide

The interview will be semi-structured. The schedule will include the following topics and questions:

Participant background

1. What is your main role in the project team?
2. How many years have you been working in the software or IT industry? In current role?

A description of the project(s) that is adopting (or adopted) DevOps practices

3. Can you please briefly (e.g., in one or two sentences) describe this project, e.g., its goals?
4. What is the domain of this project?
5. Is it a green-field project or a maintenance one?
6. How many people are involved in this project?
7. Which DevOps practices (e.g., continuous delivery and deployment, infrastructure as code, etc.) are realized by your organization in this project? Why?

Continuous Delivery/Deployment (CD) Pipeline and Automation

8. How often the primary application or service you work on is in a releasable state (production-ready)?
 - Multiple times a day
 - Once a day
 - A few times (e.g., one or two) a week
 - A few times (e.g., one or two) a month
 - A few times (e.g., one or two) a year
 - Less than once a year
9. For the primary application or service you work on, how often does your organization deploy/release to production or customer?
 - Multiple times a day
 - Once a day
 - A few times (e.g., one or two) a week
 - A few times (e.g., one or two) a month
 - A few times (e.g., one or two) a year
 - Less than once a year
10. How would you grade your CD pipeline in terms of automation? Is it fully automated?
 - i. Do changes directly go to production/customers? If no, why?

- ii. On average, how long does it take between committing code and successfully placing the code into production?
 - More than six months
 - Between one month and six months
 - Between one week and one month
 - Between one day and one week
 - Less than one day
 - Less than one hour
 - I don't know or not applicable
- iii. What challenges/issues/choke-points you have/had to set up **[fully automated] CD pipeline**?
 1. Which steps are still manual in your CD pipeline? Why?
 2. Automated acceptance tests and quality assurance/security checks are part of your CD pipeline?
- iv. How do you design the CD pipeline stages and select tools and technologies to set up CD pipeline?
 1. Any trade-off for selecting tools? Any criteria for tool choices?
- v. As a practitioner, what do you want/would like to see in a CD pipeline? Any missing features in the current CD pipeline? Any limitations in current tools?
- 11. What benefits and costs (negative aspects) DevOps practices would bring for your organization?
 - i. Are you totally happy with DevOps adoption? Any dissenting opinions?

Architecture and DevOps Practices

Deployability is a quality attribute (non-functional requirement) which means how reliably and easily an application/component/service can be deployed to a (heterogeneous) production environment.

12. Does your organization/team take into consideration the role of **software architecture** in successfully and efficiently adopting DevOps practices? If so,
 - i. Why do you think it is necessary to do this?
 - ii. What architectural characteristics correlate with DevOps?
 - iii. How do you design/change (modernize) the application architecture for this purpose, e.g., improving deployability and supporting incremental changes?
 - iv. Do you have **deployability** and **testability** in mind when designing/modernizing the application?
 1. How **deployability** and **testability** concerns impact your architecture design?
 - v. How do you **quantify** and **measure** the deployability of your system/architecture?
 1. How do you evaluate the consequence of your architectural decisions on the deployability of your system?
 2. Can you provide one example of **architectural decisions** you made for improving the deployability of your application?
 3. Can you provide one example of **technology decisions** you made for improving the deployability of your application?

4. Can you provide some examples of the sub-optimal architectural decisions that led to problems in the deployment (release) process? i.e., architectural decisions that prevented automated deployment.

vi. Potential follow-up questions:

1. Are you using microservices architecture style or monolithic architecture to enable DevOps?
2. As part of (re-) architecting your application to enable DevOps, do/did you break down the application into smaller parts? If so, how? What challenges did you face?
 - a. What criteria (e.g., **business domain** and **team autonomy**) do you use to break down an application or large service/components?
3. How could you manage database schema changes or messaging as part of (re-) architecting your application to enable DevOps?
4. How do you deploy your application/service independently of other applications/services that it depends on?
 - a. Can you make large-scale changes to your application/service design without depending on/permission from other teams?
5. How do you deal with multiple and heterogeneous environments when practicing **continuous** and **automatic** deployment?
 - a. Can you provide examples of architectural and technological decisions you made for this purpose?

(Architectural) Decision Making Process in DevOps

13. How does the adoption of DevOps change the decision-making process?
 - i. After adopting DevOps in your organization, do architects collaborate more with teams to make architecture design decisions? If so, how?
 - ii. After adopting DevOps in your organization, do you become more independent to make your own (design) decision? If so, how?
 1. Do you need to communicate and coordinate with other teams/team members to make your own decision? Why?
 - iii. What kind of data (e.g., production data, operations metrics, and runtime data) do you utilize to make informed/data-driven (architectural design) decisions?
 1. How do you use them to inform the design of products and features?

Do you have any other comments and feedback to share with us?